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The Strategy of The Republic of Indonesian Government in Dealing with Covid-19 Pandemic from the Perspective of Total War Strategy

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic demands the Indonesian Government to act against the various impacts caused through various strategies and efforts. The spread of the Covid-19 pandemic is very fast, resulting in many casualties, not only the wider community but also health workers who carry out tasks throughout the country. The existence of the Covid-19 pandemic has also affected the political, economic and almost all sectors of life, including defense. In order to discuss the problem of the Covid-19 Pandemic, supporting theories are used, namely strategy theory, pandemic theory, universal defense theory and universal war strategy theory. The method used in the analysis of the Covid-19 pandemic is a qualitative descriptive phenomenology, that is, with the existing phenomena regarding Covid-19 and qualitatively explaining the data obtained from literature studies to gain an understanding of strategies for dealing with it. The results of the analysis found that there were various supporting factors and obstacles to handling efforts, implementing strategies, among others, to increase understanding of Covid-19, then preventive steps by using the next application of governance for handling Covid-19 and increasing a strong community superstructure. The aim of the strategy undertaken is to inhibit the spread and countermeasures from a Total War Strategy perspective.

Keywords: Strategy, Government, Pandemic, Covid-19, Total War

1. Introduction

The Covid-19 Pandemic was first discovered in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, on December 31, 2019, with pneumonia symptoms in patients. On January 7, 2020, pneumonia was identified as a new type of Coronavirus (novel coronavirus), and in early 2020 was declared a global phenomenon. The spread of Pandemic is rapidly growing to become a health problem around the world. As of January 30, 2020, Covid-19 is designated a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) (ZA et al., 2020). In Indonesia, the first case was announced by President Jokowi on March 2, 2020, with two cases of Covid-19 positive patients (Ellyvon, 2020).

The defense white paper explains the various threats that Indonesia can face in the future and present. Such threats can be real threats and unreal threats—one of the real threats in the presence of disease outbreaks. Furthermore, currently, the Covid-19 Pandemic is hitting all parts of Indonesia with various consequences (Kementerian Pertahanan Republik Indonesia, 2015).

The spread of the Covid-19 virus in Indonesia quickly caused many fatalities, disruption of economic and political activities, and other life areas. Since the beginning of the spread, Indonesia has not been able to solve the Pandemic that occurred until now. Efforts to anticipate early on the spread of covid-19, up to reduce the widespread impact it causes, still have not shown satisfactory results. However, the Government has made efforts to reduce the spread of Covid-19. Until now, it has reported an increase in coronavirus cases in many regions in Indonesia. The community has heeded the advice and regulations in daily activities, such as wearing masks, applying physical distance, and washing hands.

The mortality rate in Indonesian health workers are high. According to the Chairman of the Hospital Management Department, Hasanuddin University, Irwandy, the death rate of Indonesian health workers at that time reached 6.5 percent (Pusparisa, 2020). That is, in every 100 deaths, there are about six to seven health workers who die. Meanwhile, the Vice Chairman of PB IDI (Ikatan Dokter Indonesia), dr Adib Khumaidi, said that Indonesia's death rate in June 2020 is not much different from last month's figures (Souisa, 2020).

The number of news that intersects the truth of the Covid-19 virus is also a problem in itself. According to the Director-General of Information and Public Communication of the Ministry of Communication and Information, Widodo Muktiyo, the outbreak of covid-19 in almost all the world, including Indonesia, brings up much news, especially on social media (Doni003, 2020). Ministry of Communication and Information noted that 192 hoaxes news about the virus circulated on various social media platforms (Widodo, 2020), thus causing weakness in the face. Whereas the Government should be more able to monopolize the news to deliver accurate news and not be ambiguous and become a reference for the public.

The impact of the Covid-19 outbreak is seen in almost all sectors of people's lives (Mashabi, 2020). Social activities are banned and temporarily suspended, the economy weakens, transportation services are reduced and tightly regulated, tourism is closed, shopping malls are deserted, and informal sectors are closed such as; Ojek Online, Angkot driver, street vendors, mobile traders, MSMEs, and crude porters decreased income. Trade centers, such as malls, land markets that are usually crowded visited by the community are suddenly quiet and currently closed temporarily. The tourism sector is in decline; the Government is closing tourist attractions, entertainment venues (Mutiah, 2020). Work and study are done at home online (Binus, 2020).

Referring to the above problem, the author tries to examine how the Government prepares to deal with Covid-19 and how the Indonesian Government's strategy in dealing with the covid-19 Pandemic by implementing countermeasures from all sectors of life that are total.

2. Method

This research uses a descriptive method of phenomenological qualitative. Researchers explain in detail the problems faced with existing phenomena in detail and efforts to solve them. In an effort to complete this research, researchers tried to discuss the efforts made from the perspective of the total war in the hope that efforts to combat the Covid-19 Pandemic become more accurate and successful. In this case, the data collection was done through a literature study, coupled with empirical experience during his stint as an Air Force soldier.

The main challenge faced is how the Indonesian Government's strategy in dealing with the Covid-19 Pandemic. The strategy is reviewed from the perspective of the total war to overcome the current Pandemic and anticipate similar situations by understanding various trends in the period 2020.

3. Results

3.1 Early Covid-19

In early 2020, Covid-19 became a world health problem. The case began with information from the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, 2019, that mentioned a case of pneumonia cluster with unclear etiology in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China. This case continued to develop until it was finally known that the cause of this pneumonia cluster is a novel coronavirus. The case continued to grow until there were reports of deaths and importations outside China. On January 30, 2020, WHO designated Covid-19 as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC). On February 12, 2020, WHO officially designated this novel coronavirus disease in humans as Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) (Kementerian Pertahanan, 2020). In Indonesia, the first case of Covid-19 occurred in Depok with indications of cough that has not healed since February 16, 2020. After the victim's friend's confirmation on February 28, 2020, the patient was declared a Covid-19 sufferer (Nuraini, 2020). The Government of Indonesia designates the Corona Virus or Covid-19 Outbreak as a National Disaster. The status was announced on Saturday afternoon, March 14, 2020, by the President through the Head of the National Disaster Management Agency, Doni Monardo, at the BNPB Building (Rokom, 2020).

Since the first case was announced, the number of positive cases of Covid-19 has continued to spike. On Wednesday, April 1, 2020, the number of positive cases of Covid-19 reached 1,677 cases, with 103 patients declared cured and 157 patients dying (Nuraini, 2020).

Figure 1: Covid-19 Pandemic Graphic in Indonesia

Source: National Task Force for Handling Covid-19 BNPB, 2020

From the chart above until December 3, 2020, there is still an increase in cases of the Covid-19 Pandemic in Indonesia every day, starting from the announcement of the Covid-19 Pandemic as a national disaster. The Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic in Indonesia to date has not indicated a decrease in the number of positive patients. Based on the latest data accessed on the www.covid.go.id page, the number of Covid-19 cases can be seen from the growing number of patients every day. In order to suppress the spread of Covid-19, the Government continues to implement various efforts (Puspita, 2020).

Table 1: Data on 5 Highest Case Provinces

No	Loc	Cases	Cured	Death
1	Jakarta	149.018	134.272	2.882
2	East Java	67.613	58.770	4.740
3	Center Java	63.610	43.316	2.544
4	West Java	63.043	51.727	1.025
5	South Sulawesi	22.402	19.269	512

Source: National Task Force for Handling Covid-19 BNPB, Dec 11, 2020

From the table above, it can be seen that the highest Covid-19 cases occurred in East Java, with a death rate of 4,493 people. The three areas that occupy the next highest death position are DKI Jakarta, as many as 2732, and Central Java, of 2409 people.

Based on government data entered until Tuesday (8/9/2020) at 12.00 WIB, 3,046 people were declared positive for Covid-19 in the last 24 hours. Thus, the number of Covid-19 cases in Indonesia has now reached 200,035 people, starting from the first patient's announcement on March 2, 2020 (Mashabi, 2020).

3.2 Economic impact

Restrictions on public activities affect business activities that then impact the economy. This August Central Statistics Agency (BPS) report stated that Indonesia's economic growth in the second quarter of 2020 was minus 5.32 percent. Previously, in the first quarter of 2020, BPS reported that Indonesia's economic growth only grew by 2.97 percent, down from 5.02 percent growth in the same period in 2019. The weakening economic performance also has an impact on the employment situation in Indonesia. SMERU Research Institute, an independent institution that conducts public research and studies, in August 2020 released their policy note entitled "Anticipating the Potential Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic Crisis on the Employment Sector". On that note, the SMERU research team underlined that there are at least two implications of Indonesia's economic crisis in the employment sector. First, an increase in the number of unemployed and a change in the post-crisis labor market landscape (Rizal, 2020).

Of the total Rp 695.2 trillion, the details, amounting to Rp 87.55 trillion for the health budget, social protection budget of Rp 203.9 trillion, business incentives of Rp 120.61 trillion, amounting to Rp 123.46 trillion prepared for the MSME sector, corporate financing to Rp 53.57 trillion, and for sectoral support K/L and Local Government of Rp 106.11 trillion. Justin explained that as a consequence of the additional costs to deal with Covid-19, the budget deficit in 2020 is expected to widen, from the deficit of 1.76 percent or Rp 307.2 trillion to 5.07 percent or Rp 852 trillion in Perpres 54/2020, and the new deficit is estimated at 6.34 percent or Rp 1,039.2 trillion. "In other words, there is an estimated increase in financing needs of Rp 905.2 trillion, from Rp 741.8 trillion to Rp 1,647.1 trillion," explained Yustinus (Fauzia, 2020).

Director-General of Tax of the Ministry of Finance (Kemenkeu) Suryo Utomo revealed three major impacts of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Indonesian economy to enter a crisis period. The first impact is to make household consumption, or purchasing power, which is a 60 percent support to the economy falls quite deep. This is evidenced by BPS data, which records that household consumption fell from 5.02 percent in the first quarter of 2019 to 2.84 percent in the first quarter of this year. The second impact is that the Pandemic creates prolonged uncertainty so that investment weakens and implies a business cessation. The third impact is that the whole world is weakening the economy, causing commodity prices to fall, and Indonesia's exports to several countries also stalled (Zuraya, 2020).

3.3 Social impact

At the beginning of its appearance, the virus received a variety of responses that emerged from the People of Indonesia. Some begin to be cautious and implement healthy lifestyles, but more do not care and seem to underestimate; even make this virus a joke. Not only ordinary people but officials also underestimated the existence of this virus and did not make preparations or anticipation of the emergence of this outbreak in Indonesia. Even as COVID-19 began to spread rapidly to various regions, and some countries have closed access in and out, the Government and citizens of Indonesia still seem relaxed and do less to prevent this virus (Salsabila, 2020).

Uncertainty, confusion, and emergencies caused by the Coronavirus can be a stressor for many people. The uncertainty in knowing when the outbreak will end makes many groups of people, especially the lower middle class, confused about their fate. A life that goes on as usual without a livelihood makes it difficult for them to make ends meet. The existence of the Coronavirus that threatens everyone is likely to become a stressor for most people, and the impact can be just as severe as the impact if infected by the Coronavirus (Taylor, 2019).

3.4 The news

Various kinds of news that are difficult to distinguish right and wrong sometimes arise from the government. For example, through online media coverage, the government provides funds to combat the Covid-19 Pandemic through the 2020 State Budget of Rp 405.1 trillion, as explained by the Minister of Finance, Sri Mulyani Indrawati (Puspita, 2020). On another occasion, the Ministry of Finance (MoF) confirmed that the budget for handling the coronavirus pandemic (Covid-19) and the national economic recovery program (PEN) amounted to Rp 695.2 trillion (Putri, 2020). Previously, Finance Minister Sri Mulyani Indrawati revealed on her Instagram account @smindrawati about the Pandemic handling budget and pen program of Rp 905.2 trillion (Putri, 2020). Special Staff of Finance Minister Yustinus Prastowo conveyed word writing error to Kompas.com through a WA message, Friday (6/19/2020) night (Putri, 2020). Furthermore, the government plans to adjust the budget for handling covid-19 to Rp 695.2 trillion (Putri, 2020).

3.5 Indonesian Government Strategy

The Central Government, through the Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19, makes four strategies that will be consistently carried out to strengthen physical distancing policy as a basic strategy to overcome the Covid-19 Pandemic (Wibowo, 2020).

- a. Movement masks for all with mandatory campaigns to use masks when in public places or outdoors
- b. Tracing of positive cases treated using Rapid Test or rapid test,
- c. The third strategy is the education and preparation of isolation independently in some tracing results that show reactive test results from rapid tests or negatives with symptoms to perform self-isolation
- d. The fourth strategy is hospital isolation for patients who show clinical symptoms who need services at the Hospital

The next strategy is in accordance with what President Jokowi said at a video conference on Tuesday, March 31, 2020, that government regulations (PP) on Large-Scale Social Restrictions and the Presidential Decree on the determination of public health emergencies have been published (Egeham, 2020). Government Regulation No. 21 of 2020 concerning Large-Scale Social Restrictions to Accelerate the Handling of Covid-19, known by the abbreviation PSBB (Siska, 2020). PSBB is a restriction on certain activities of residents in an area suspected of being infected with Covid-19 in order to prevent its spread. PSBB is carried out during the longest incubation period, which is 14 days. If there is still evidence of a new case, it can be extended within 14 days of the discovery of the last case (Syafriada, 2020). PSBB measures include school holidays, business premises, places of worship, and restrictions on people's social activities outside the home. With PSBB, the industry is also forced to adjust until the outbreak can be controlled, with all the consequences (Yurianto, 2020).

Article 13 decree No. 9 of 2020 regulates various activities limited by PSBB, namely: a) school and workplace holidays; b) restrictions on religious activities; c) restrictions on activities in public places or facilities; d) restrictions on social and cultural activities; e) restriction of transportation modes; f) Restrictions on other activities specifically related to aspects of defense and security This policy authorizes the Minister of Health to establish PSBB in a region based on a request from the Regional Head (governor or regent/major). The government has also issued a policy through Presidential Decree No. 12 of 2020 concerning the Determination of Non-Natural Disasters for the Spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) as a National Disaster.

4. Discussion

4.1 Why the Total War Strategy?

Some of the reasons that can be used as answers to the question of why total war strategies are used in an effort to deal with the Covid-19 Pandemic are as follows: the first is that the Covid-19 Pandemic outbreak has damaged and disrupted various areas of life, therefore tackling pandemic outbreaks must involve all components of the nation. As discussed above, through the definition of total war, the empowerment of all components of the nation both politically, economically, and security defense becomes important as a holistic collective power. In a broad sense that all components of the nation and in any strata affect the efforts carried out in the face of covid-19. Politically, the Government plays a role in making policies that support each other in various fields. This policy will be able to be used as a control so that the spread, covid-19 countermeasures can be implemented properly. The interdependence of various sectors is impossible to separate in the face of the current pandemic. The policies made must be in line as a whole and thoroughly. Such policies should always be within government control. So, the reason to use the total war in the face of covid-19 is so that the policies put in place and made by the Government can support each other successfully facing the covid-19 Pandemic.

The Second Pandemic, Covid-19, is an outbreak that is very easily transmitted through droplets and air. This causes more and more people to contract it easily when each component is not mutually supportive and apathetic. At least by involving all nation components, it will facilitate isolation against the spread and control of its impact. Therefore, in order for control efforts that can be done quickly, everyone or groups of people must always be in preparedness. The preparedness measures carried out are inseparable from outbreak management principles, namely in the prevention phase, detection phase, and response phase. In the prevention phase, what needs to be done is to make preparedness guidelines that refer to the Health Quarantine Law and the Infectious Disease Outbreak Law so as to support the implementation of global governance of outbreak management; submit a circular on Covid-19 prevention preparedness to all stakeholders, especially the provincial health office/district/city (Putri, 2020).

Moreover, the third is a rapid recovery to the impossible impact of partial implementation because the total war strategy is a recommended option. Professor of Political Psychology from the University of Indonesia (UI) Prof. Dr. Hamdi Muluk, M.Si, said that in the face of this pandemic, solidarity and mutual awareness could be strengthened by utilizing the nation's strong social capital. Because this nation has strong social capital such as gotong royong, for example, working together to stay at home to stop the spread of the virus.

Viewed from the Economic side, handling covid-19 must be prioritized in countermeasures. Various sectors of the economy can hinder the running of pandemic management efforts. Therefore, the Government needs to be selective in passing efforts to help the community in maintaining economic sustainability.

Socio-cultural factors can make a new way of life or pattern that can be implemented to implement the covid-19 Pandemic properly. Critical points in the community can be addressed with a new pattern of life being implemented. The use of masks wherever and whenever active, keeping distance with people who are considered potentially infected with Covid-19 or not, and always maintain personal hygiene, especially hands and faces throughout the day wherever they are.

Repeated misreporting makes people apathetic to inconsistent government policies. This has a severe impact on the Government's efforts to implement strategic policy socialization and must receive a positive response from the community in its implementation. Therefore, to maximize the Government's strategy in handling the Covid-19 Pandemic, it sets out a one-door information strategy. The Government also needs to consistently apply the rules fairly by providing punishment and reward, which applies in general.

Disaster management or Covid-19 outbreak is currently handled by BNPB (National Disaster Management Agency) because the Covid-19 Pandemic can be qualified as a non-natural disaster. BNPB has implemented maximum efforts in pandemic management amid the limitations. Handling the covid-19 Pandemic requires special qualifications and expertise, especially in anticipation of a pandemic that may occur in the future.

Based on Law No. 2 of 2002 on Defense. The country's defense system in the face of military threats places government agencies outside the field of defense as the main element, in accordance with the shape and nature of the threat faced with the support of other elements of the nation's strength. Based on Law No. 2, the Covid-19 Pandemic in an effort to deal with and counteract the Covid-19 Pandemic needs to have a body that is following the shape and nature of the threat which currently, the agency that specializes in dealing with pandemics as intended does not yet exist then it is necessary to form a special agency to anticipate supervising and researching disasters caused by bacteria or viruses that can turn into Pandemics.

Therefore, in anticipation of similar events in the future, it is very appropriate so that the Government better prepares itself early for the existence of special bodies that work to anticipate, overcome and overcome outbreaks/pandemics. Special bodies are directly responsible to the President. They can implement a variety of appropriate and comprehensive strategies so that future Pandemic outbreaks can be adequately addressed, not resulting in many fatalities, not disrupting economic and political, and socio-cultural life. The special agency is tasked to anticipate various possibilities related to viruses or bacteria that can turn into a deadly Pandemic. Specialized agencies work throughout the year later in a time when no Pandemic can work as researchers in anticipation of bacteria or viruses that may be able to develop. The special agency is also a countermeasure coordinator so that coordination with agencies that deal with Covid-19 problems in various fields and levels can be well established. Likewise, regarding preaching, it can be synthesized from the right sources.

The ability that must be possessed by the special agent is the handling of the Covid-19 Pandemic, including anticipating, predicting, preventing, tackling, coordinating, and carrying out research on bacteria or viruses that are capable or can be used as biological weapons. The special body consists of various military practitioners, physician or expert health practitioners, think-tankers, economists, psychology experts, public health experts, and other related experts.

4.2 Strategies implemented

In order to face the Covid-19 strategy implemented from the perspective of the total war, including the main strategy, reserve strategy, and supporting strategy. The main core of the activities facing the Covid-19 Pandemic, in general, is the prevention of the second is handling, and the third is recovery. In implementing prevention, several innovations are implemented to implement prevention; an example is the application of Covid-19.

The first is the Main strategy, implemented by medical personnel. This strategy aims to ensure that there is no status improvement for people in the surrounding environment to become Supervised Person (ODP), Patient Under Surveillance (PDP), or Suspect. Furthermore, intensive supervision so that ODP, PDP, or Suspect is not confirmed Covid-19 and the third is to perform curative actions, namely treatment of people who have been confirmed Covid-19. In order to ensure the implementation of this same strategy, it is necessary to form a unit that is ready to move in a short time in order to anticipate preventive activities carried out or implemented by the Government so that the efforts of strategies carried out by the Government can be carried out properly.

The second is a reserve strategy aimed at dealing with the continuing wave of pandemic spread/transmission. Experts found that this disaster has different implications for how the central/local Government allocates resources, especially resources that have never been optimally utilized. The rapid contagion effect means that the Government should be able to allocate resources effectively. Government policy is the main determinant of the size of the pandemic disaster. Mistakes in political decision-making will impact the number of costs to overcome the Pandemic and losses, both fatalities, exposure amounts, and economic losses (ZA et al., 2020). To reduce anxiety in the community, we should do various things to increase public optimism in the midst of this Pandemic. People who can still provide for their lives are increasing their care by contributing to help the poor by doing fundraising and making donations (Salsabila, 2020).

In addition, it is also necessary to prepare a strategy that is a supporting strategy that is the first to form a crisis center, which is an organization led by a person who has managerial abilities and is ready to carry out regulations and communicate to the community and Government. The second prepares medical personnel, and then the third prepares an information technology-based control system that makes pro-active fiscal policy so as to ensure economic resilience. The last is that logistics is managed professionally by the central and local governments so that logistics distribution channels intended to support Covid-19 countermeasures or recovery activities are not constrained.

5. Conclusion

Covid-19 is one of the real threats faced today, which has resulted in fatalities, broad economic impacts, and social impacts. The Government has implemented various efforts in anticipating, overcoming, and tackling the impacts caused by Covid-19. Efforts to overcome are carried out holistically involving all components of the nation because the Pandemic has damaged and disrupted various areas of life, so as to overcome it involves all components of the nation. The strategies implemented in pandemic management implemented through the application of total warfare strategies are very relevant and suitable in order to overcome the situation faced by all components of the nation. Public awareness by jointly being a big part of the Indonesian nation is very decisive in the success of the government's efforts.

In anticipation of pandemics, the Government is better prepared early through special agencies that anticipate, overcome, and overcome outbreaks/pandemics. Special agencies are directly responsible to the President and can implement a variety of appropriate and comprehensive strategies so that future Pandemic outbreaks can be appropriately addressed. Strategies implemented to deal with Covid-19 from a total war perspective include key strategies, backup strategies, and supporting strategies. The primary strategy, implemented by medical personnel, aims to restrain the increasing status of pandemic victims, while the reserve strategy aimed at dealing with the continuing wave of pandemic spread /transmission and supporting strategies, among others, is to form a crisis center, prepare medical personnel, prepare control systems, fiscal and logistics policies.

References

- Allianz Indonesia. (2020). *Yuk, Pahami Lebih Jelas Arti Pandemi pada COVID-19 | Explore | Perusahaan Asuransi Allianz Indonesia*. <https://www.allianz.co.id/explore/detail/yuk-pahami-lebih-jelas-arti-pandemi-pada-covid-19/101490>.
- Bartholomees, B. (2010). The U.S. ARMY War College Guide to National Security Issues. In *Challenges: Vol. I Theory A* (4th ed., Issue July). <http://www.StrategicStudiesInstitute.army.mil/>.
<http://www.carlisle.army.mil/ssi>
- Binus. (2020). *Belajar dan Bekerja dari Rumah , Pendekatan Baru Adaptasi Teknologi*. <https://binus.ac.id/2020/03/belajar-dan-bekerja-dari-rumah-pendekatan-baru-adaptasi-teknologi/>
- Doni003. (2020). *Kementerian Komunikasi dan Informatika*. Kominfo.Go.Id. https://www.kominfo.go.id/content/detail/30688/dirjen-ikp-90-persen-berita-hoaks-diedarkan-secara-sengaja/0/berita_satker

- Egeham, L. (2020). *Jokowi Teken PP Pembatasan Sosial Berskala Besar dan Keppres Kedaruratan Kesehatan*. Liputan6.Com. <http://djsn.go.id/index.php/berita/detail/jokowi-teken-pp-pembatasan-sosial-berskala-besar-dan-keppres-kedaruratan-kesehatan>
- Ellyvon, P. (2020). *Diumumkan Awal Maret, Ahli: Virus Corona Masuk Indonesia dari Januari*. Kompas.Com. <https://www.kompas.com/sains/read/2020/05/11/130600623/diumumkan-awal-maret-ahli--virus-corona-masuk-indonesia-dari-januari.%0Ahttps://www.kompas.com/sains/read/2020/05/11/130600623/diumumkan-awal-maret-ahli--virus-corona-masuk-indonesia-dari-januari>
- Fauzia, M. (2020). *Kemenkeu Tegaskan Anggaran Penanganan Covid-19 Rp 695,2 Triliun*. <https://money.kompas.com/read/2020/06/20/100200226/kemenkeu-tegaskan-anggaran-penanganan-covid-19-rp-695-2-triliun>
- Kementerian Pertahanan. (2020). *Sekjen Kemhan: Kemandirian Indhan Penting Dalam Mewujudkan Sistem Pertahanan Negara yang Kuat*. Kemhan.Go.Id. file:///Users/budi/Documents/Kuliah Unhan/Jurnal /Sekjen Kemhan- Kemandirian Indhan Penting Dalam Mewujudkan Sistem Pertahanan Negara yang Kuat.webarchive
- Kementerian Pertahanan Republik Indonesia. (2015). *Buku Putih Pertahanan Indonesia*. In *kemhan.go.id* (3rd ed.). Kementerian Pertahanan Republik Indonesia. www.kemhan.go.id
- Mashabi, S. (2020). *Update: Kasus Covid-19 Tembus 200.000, Pemerintah Bentuk Tim Percepatan Vaksin*. Puspensos.Kemsos.Go.Id. <https://nasional.kompas.com/read/2020/09/09/06163691/update-kasus-covid-19-tembus-200000-pemerintah-bentuk-tim-percepatan-vaksin?page=all>
- Mutiah, D. (2020). *Sektor Pariwisata Nyaris Tumbang Akibat Corona Covid-19, Menparekraf Masih Siapkan Solusi*. Liputan6.Com. <https://www.liputan6.com/lifestyle/read/4209455/sektor-pariwisata-nyaris-tumbang-akibat-corona-covid-19-menparekraf-masih-siapkan-solusi>
- Nuraini, T. (2020). *Kronologi Munculnya Covid-19 di Indonesia Hingga Terbit Keppres Darurat Kesehatan*. Merdeka.Com. <https://www.merdeka.com/trending/kronologi-munculnya-covid-19-di-indonesia-hingga-terbit-keppres-darurat-kesehatan-klm.html>
- Ovier, A. (2020). *HUT Ke-75, TNI Dituntut Tingkatkan Kemampuan Hadapi Ancaman Hibrida*. Beritasatu.Com. <https://www.beritasatu.com/asnie-ovier/nasional/683605/hut-ke75-tni-dituntut-tingkatkan-kemampuan-hadapi-ancaman-hibrida>
- Prabowo, J. (2019). *Pokok pokok pemikiran tentang perang semesta* (3rd ed.). Tamaprint Indonesia.
- Pusparisa, Y. (2020). *Tingkat Kematian Tenaga Kesehatan Indonesia Mencapai 6,5%*. Databoks. <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2020/05/15/tingkat-kematian-tenaga-kesehatan-indonesia-mencapai-65>
- Puspita, M. U. (2020). *Pelaksanaan Anggaran Pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19*. Artikel DJKN. <https://www.djkn.kemenkeu.go.id/kanwil-suluttenggomalu/baca-artikel/13163/Pelaksanaan-Anggaran-Pada-Masa-Pandemi-Covid-19.html>
- Putri, S. N. S. (2020). *Kesiapsiagaan Indonesia Menghadapi Potensi Penyebaran Corona*. *Pusat Penelitian Badan Keahlian DPR RI, XII(3)*, 14–18. https://berkas.dpr.go.id/puslit/files/info_singkat/Info_Singkat-XII-3-I-P3DI-Februari-2020-1957.pdf
- Rachman, A. (2013). *Peran Satuan Teritorial Dalam Menghadapi Perang Generasi Keempat*. Seskoad.
- Rizal, J. G. (2020). *Pandemi Covid-19, Apa Saja Dampak pada Sektor Ketenagakerjaan Indonesia?* Kompas.Com. <https://www.kompas.com/tren/read/2020/08/11/102500165/pandemi-covid-19-apa-saja-dampak-pada-sektor-ketenagakerjaan-indonesia-?page=all>
- Rokom. (2020). *Status wabah Corona di Indonesia ditetapkan sebagai bencana nasional*. Sehat Negeriku! <http://sehatnegeriku.kemkes.go.id/baca/rilis-media/20200315/3633379/status-wabah-corona-indonesia-ditetapkan-bencana-nasional/>
- Salsabila, N. (2020). *Perubahan Yang Terjadi Dalam Masyarakat Sebagai Dampak Dari Covid-19*. Universitas Brawijaya. <https://fisip.ub.ac.id/?p=10282&lang=id>
- Siska, D. (2020). *PSBB: Upaya Strategis Penanganan Covid-19? | Padek*. Jawapos.Com. <https://padek.jawapos.com/opini/11/05/2020/psbb-upaya-strategis-penanganan-covid-19/>
- Souisa, H. (2020). *Sejumlah Alasan Tingginya Kematian Tenaga Kesehatan Indonesia Saat Pandemi Virus Corona*. Abc.Net. <https://www.abc.net.au/indonesian/2020-06-24/tingginya-kematian-tenaga-kesehatan-di-indonesia-karena-covid-19/12385556>
- Syafrida, S. (2020). *Bersama Melawan Virus Covid 19 di Indonesia*. *SALAM: Jurnal Sosial Dan Budaya Syar-i*, 7(6). <https://doi.org/10.15408/sjsbs.v7i6.15325>
- Taylor, S. (2019). *Coronaphobia: Fear and the 2019-nCoV outbreak*. *Department of Psychiatry, University of British Columbia, Canada*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102196>
- Wibowo, A. (2020). *Empat Strategi Pemerintah Atasi COVID-19*. Gugus Tugas Percepatan Penanganan COVID-19. <https://bnpb.go.id/berita/empat-strategi-pemerintah-atasi-covid19>

- Widodo, L. (2020). *Ada 192 Berita Hoax Terkait Virus Covid 19*. Wwww.Suaramerdeka.Com.
<https://www.suaramerdeka.com/news/nasional/221556-ada-192-berita-hoax-terkait-virus-covid-19>
- Yarger, H. R. (2006). *Toward a Theory of Strategy: Art Lykke and the Army War College Strategy Model*. *U.S. Army War College, June*, 107–113.
<https://marshallcenterciss.contentdm.oclc.org/digital/collection/p16378coll5/id/417/>
- Yurianto, A. (2020). *Menyingkap Tabir Strategi PSBB untuk Penanganan Covid-19 - hukumonline*.
Hukumonline.Com. <https://www.hukumonline.com/berita/baca/lt5ec50d0cb7297/menyingkap-tabir-strategi-psbb-untuk-penanganan-covid-19/>
- ZA, S., Putra, D. I., Sofyan, S., & Bimo. (2020). *Pedoman Umum Menghadapi Pandemi Covid-19 Bagi Pemerintah Daerah*. Menteri Dalam Negeri. <https://covid19.kemkes.go.id/protokol-covid-19/pedoman-umum-menghadapi-pandemi-covid-19-bagi-pemerintah-daerah/>
- Zuraya, N. (2020). *Tiga Dampak Besar Pandemi Covid-19 bagi Ekonomi RI | Republika Online*.
<https://republika.co.id/berita/qdgt5p383/tiga-dampak-besar-pandemi-covid19-bagi-ekonomi-ri>